

APPENDIX A – QUESTIONS ASKED THROUGH THE FALA.BR PLATFORM

1. after the publication of Decree No. 9,203/2017, is there a Risk Management Plan?
2. Is there an Integrity Plan after the publication of Decree No. 9,203/2017 or Decree No. 11,529/2023?
3. If you have the Risk Management Plan and/or Integrity Plan, do they include risks related to integrity according to the concept outlined in Ordinance 57/2019 of the CGU?
 - 3.1 If yes, could you describe how these risks are defined?
 - 3.2 If yes, how are they being managed?
 - 3.3 If yes, how is the information derived from integrity risk management used and integrated into decision-making by this agency? Provide examples of how this information influences decisions.
4. Besides Risk Management Plans, is there evidence of this Plan's practical and effective implementation? How is this implementation verified or evaluated within the agency?

Note: Please attach the Plans to the Platform or provide a link to download them. Any other documents that demonstrate this agency's concern with Risk Management (e.g., policy, program, ordinances, code of ethics or conduct, manuals, guides, etc.) may be attached to the response.

INTEGRITY RISK MANAGEMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Integrity Risk Management

Welcome to the questionnaire on risk management in public administration. Your participation is crucial to deepen our understanding and improve practices related to risk management and integrity in public administration.

We kindly ask that you fill out the questions directly, providing as much information as possible. Your contribution is vital to the continuous improvement of this fundamental aspect of public administration.

Your answers are confidential and will be used exclusively for research purposes.

We guarantee that your personal information will not be disclosed. Feel free to answer with complete honesty. Qual o seu cargo/função na Instituição?

- 1) What is your position/function in the Institution?
- 2) What is your position/function in the Institution?
- 3) Regarding gender identity, how do you identify yourself?
- 4) Do you only perform this function related to Risk Management in your institution or do you combine functions (with risk management being a complementary function)?
- 5) Could you tell me where the definition of what a Risk Management Plan (RMP) means is written?
- 6) In your opinion, do you think it is more efficient to consult the risks in the Risk Management Plan before integrating them into the Integrity Plan?
- 7) Do you have the capacity to suggest a training path for the "team" that works directly involved in risk management, including integrity aspects?
- 8) Do you have the capacity to suggest a comprehensive training path for "all employees at different levels" of the institution, focused on public integrity, including integrity risk management?
- 9) In your opinion, is it more interesting to have only one Plan that covers both (a Risk Management Plan and an Integrity Plan)?
- 10) In your institution, in addition to your sector, is there another that deals with the topic of "Integrity" or is it in the same sector as yours?
- 11) Have you taken any training on the topic of Risk Management or something similar in the last 2 years? 12) In your opinion, are there sufficient courses/training at the School of Government or other institutions on the subject of risk management, integrity or similar?
- 13) How often does the Risk Management Committee/Council or similar meet to monitor and address risks? (monthly, bimonthly, quarterly, four-monthly, half-yearly, annually, others...)
- 14) Does senior management believe that Risk Management is important to the organization?
- 15) Does the institution (senior management/Committees/Councils) take into account the information that efficient risk management can provide?
- 16) If you answered yes to the previous question, give examples of how they use the information for decision-making.
- 17) How long could you and your team be away from work to attend an in-person training course on risk management without compromising your duties?
- 18) Are those involved in Risk Management qualified to act in monitoring and monitoring risks to integrity? 19) What are the main challenges faced in implementing risk management in your institution?
- 20) What opportunities do you identify to improve risk management in your institution?

- 21) What tangible benefits has integrity risk management provided to your agency?
- 22) Is there any technological solution used to monitor and track risk management?
- 23) If you answered yes to the previous question, what would that technological solution be?
- 24) What actions have been taken to raise awareness and engage employees in integrity risk management in the last year?
- 25) How are dialogue and transparent communication about risks encouraged in the workplace?
- 26) In your opinion, are there any regulatory/legal gaps that can be improved in relation to risk management, including integrity risk?
- 27) Is there any mechanism for sharing good practices related to risk management among different sectors and organizations?
- 28) Is there any additional information you would like to share about risk management in public administration?

Thank you for your participation! Your responses are essential for the continuous improvement of risk management in public administration. We hope to count on your collaboration in future initiatives.